

Prevalence of Pathogenic *E. coli* O157:H7 from Diverse Sources in Negele Town, West Guji, Ethiopia

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Abstract:

E. coli O157: H7 is widely recognized as a major foodborne pathogen responsible for diarrhoea, haemorrhagic colitis, and haemolytic-uremic syndrome. This study was carried out in Negele town to determine the prevalence of *E. coli* O157: H7 in cow flesh, water streams, and soil. A systematic random sampling technique was utilized to gather samples, which were then transported to Bule Hora University's biology laboratory for isolation and identification of *E. coli* O157: H7. The colonies identified as *E. coli* were streaked onto Sorbitol-MacConkey agar and cultured at 37°C for 24 hours. *E.*

coli O157:H7 was verified using a latex agglutination kit. *E. coli* O157: H7 isolates were tested for antimicrobial susceptibility in vitro against nine different antibiotics. The data was analyzed using SPSS 21 software. The Pearson Chi-square test was used, and differences were judged significant at $P \leq .05$. Descriptive statistics such as crosstabulation were used to determine the percentage of prevalence in samples. From a total of samples, the overall prevalence of *E. coli* O157: H7 in cow meat, soils, and streams was determined to be 6.25%, 4%, and 6.66%. The abattoir stores had the highest prevalence of *E. coli* O157: H7 (3.3%) compared to retailer shops (1.7%). Doxycycline, Ciprofloxacin, and Gentamicin demonstrated the highest susceptibility. Tetracycline was shown to have the highest resistance. Multidrug resistance was shown to be common among isolates. This investigation confirmed a significant prevalence of *E. coli* O157:H7. Proper training and supervision of meat handlers, farmers, and health care personnel was strongly advised.

Keywords: *Antimicrobial susceptibility, E. coli* O157: H7, Monitoring, Multidrug resistance, Prevalence.

Introduction

Foodborne infections are the major cause of sickness and mortality in underdeveloped nations, resulting in billions of dollars in medical and societal expenditures (Agüeria, Terni et al., 2018). *Escherichia coli* O157:H7 (*E. coli* O157) is a prominent foodborne bacterium that causes serious infections in people. *Escherichia coli*

O157:H7 (*E. coli* O157) is a major public health hazard worldwide. This zoonotic disease, which is mostly carried by cattle, wreaks havoc by creating powerful Shiga toxins (Stx) that cause a variety of ailments in humans. *E. coli* O157 infections can cause excruciating cramps and bloody diarrhea in hemorrhagic colitis (HC), as well as life-threatening complications in hemolytic uremic syndrome (HUS). Recent

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studies show that *E. coli* O157 is still present in the food chain, particularly in cattle and beef products (Akomoneh et al., 2020; Peters et al., 2017). The incidence of *E. coli* O157 varies with geographical location, animal husbandry practices, and food processing techniques. Understanding its prevalence is critical for developing effective control measures and protecting public health. This introduction establishes the framework for investigating the present occurrence of *E. coli* O157 in various contexts. Understanding the prevalence of *E. coli* O157 is essential for developing effective control methods. This incidence varies significantly throughout geography, affected by factors such as animal husbandry practices and food processing technologies. Limited studies on the ecology of *E. coli* O157: H7/NM have been reported, particularly in developing countries (Rahimi and Nayeypour, 2012), where there is still an alarming rate of insanitary conditions, malnutrition, and poor health facilities. There is an urgent need to study this organism and its characteristics in order to reduce the human hazard caused by this emerging pathogen (Isibor et al., 2013), and Ethiopia is no exception. For example, a 2014 study in Ethiopia found a worrying prevalence of 10.2% in raw meat samples from several categories (beef, sheep, and goat) (Gebreyesus et al., 2014). In contrast, research in industrialized countries frequently show lower figures, emphasizing the impact of stronger rules and cleanliness standards. Beyond geographic differences, the frequency of *E. coli* O157 might vary among individual groups. Children under the age of five appear to be more vulnerable, according to a 2022 study in Ethiopia that found a 15.3% prevalence of *E. coli* O157-related diarrhea in this age range (Taye et al., 2022). A 2014 study in Addis Abeba discovered a 10.2% prevalence in raw meat samples across three categories (beef, sheep, and goat) (Gebreyesus et al., 2014). This illustrates the potential for contamination at several points in the food supply chain. Furthermore, current research delves into the worrying incidence of *E. coli* O157 among various Ethiopian groups. This emphasizes the importance of targeted measures to safeguard these vulnerable populations, which

may include improved sanitation practices and hygiene education. The occurrence of *E. coli* O157 is exacerbated by the rise of antibiotic resistance. A 2021 study from Gondar, Ethiopia, looked at the antibiotic resistance profiles of *E. coli* O157 obtained from livestock. The study found resistance to several antibiotics frequently used to treat illnesses, raising worries about the possibility of limited treatment options (Feleke et al., 2021). The outbreak of human cases caused by *E. coli* O157:H7 has been related to beef meat and raw milk, as well as other dairy products, vegetables, unpasteurized fruit juices, and water. The lack of robust surveillance of food pathogens in Ethiopian meat and meat products complicates risk-based approaches to improving food safety, as it becomes difficult to demonstrate the degree of contamination with this infection. *E. coli* O157: H7 diarrhoeal disease has been documented in several African nations, including South Africa, the Central African Republic, Kenya, Uganda, Gabon, Nigeria, and the Ivory Coast (Raji et al., 2006). In recent years, there has been an increase in research in numerous parts of Ethiopia on the incidence of *E. coli* O157: H7 and its transmission via various channels. Beef, goat, and sheep are common meats in Ethiopia, and they can often be eaten uncooked or undercooked. This could lead to an increase in the number of food-borne illnesses caused by EHEC. *E. coli* O157: H7 is introduced into agricultural soils when cattle and other ruminant feces are utilized as manure. The infection is also spread to neighboring freshwater bodies such as rivers and streams via runoff (Myataza et al., 2017). *E. coli* O157: H7 spreads down the food chain and eventually to human consumers when agricultural produce grown on contaminated soil comes into touch with the pathogen or filthy water is used to irrigate the farm's crops. Vegetables grown on manure amended soil are highly likely to be contaminated with *E. coli* O157: H7 (Saeed et al., 2013), and contamination routes include not only direct contact with the pathogen but also passive diffusion from the soil through plant roots into edible plant parts (Solomon et al., 2002). Fresh produce contamination with *E. coli* O157: H7 is well documented (Chang et al., 2013; Abadias et

al., 2012). As a result, the purpose of this study was to determine the prevalence of *E. coli* O157: H7, as no studies had been conducted and there was a lack of information and research on the prevalence of this pathogenic *E. coli* O157: H7 from sources such as cattle, water, and soils in Negele town. The study's findings will be important and beneficial for health care providers and municipal authorities in Negele to raise awareness about this pathogenic *E. coli* and take adequate precautions to prevent *E. coli* O157: H7-transmitted diarrhoea or haemolytic-uremic illnesses.

Materials and Methods

Study Area: Geographic Location of Negele Town

This study was conducted in Negele, Oromia Regional State, East Guji Zone, Ethiopia. It is located 595 kilometers south of the country's capital city, Addis Abeba. It is located at latitude $7^{\circ} 21' 36.00''$ N. and longitude $38^{\circ} 40' 12.00''$ E., with an elevation of 1450-1550msl. Negele town has three kebele administrations. The research area experiences fast population expansion. The town now has a population of 56,777, with 27,836 females and 28,941 males.

Figure 1. Map of the Study Area

Study Design

A cross-sectional investigation was carried out to investigate the prevalence of *E. coli* O157: H7 isolated from three different sources: raw meat (beef, sheep, and goat), water sources, and soils in Negele town. The key sample sites include randomly selected meat shops, bodies of water with access to cattle for drinking and bathing, and vegetable-growing soils fertilized with bovine manure.

A total of 240 raw meat samples (80 beef, 80 sheep, and 80 goat) were gathered at random from chosen abattoir shops in town. Sixty water samples were obtained from two distinct streams (30 samples from each), which are frequently used for cattle drinking and bathing. 100 soil samples (20 x 5) were obtained from the same soils where specific veggies thrive.

Sample Size Determination

The sample size (for beef, sheep and goat) was determined based on the expected prevalence of *E. coli* O157: H7 and the desired absolute precision according to the formula stated on Thrusfield (2007).

$$n=1.96^2P_{\text{exp}}(1-P_{\text{exp}})/d^2 \quad (1)$$

Where: n = required sample size;
 P_{exp} = Expected prevalence; d = desired absolute precision.

Based on a previous studies done elsewhere, the prevalence rates of *E. coli* O157: H7 in cattle was considered as 3-5%. Using this expected prevalence, 95% confidence interval and 5% absolute precision, sample size was determined as shown

$$n=1.96^2P_{\text{exp}}(1-P_{\text{exp}})/d^2$$

$$n= 3.84 \times 0.03 (1-0.03) / (0.05)^2 = 45$$

Therefore, the minimum sample size was 45 but to increase the precision, fivefold of the minimum sample size was taken and 225 of animals plus additional 15 samples were used for the study to make a total of 240.

Sample collection procedure for meat samples

The collecting process for meat samples was carried out in accordance with Bekele et al. (2021). Swab samples were collected aseptically from meat stores using a simple random sampling method. The abdomen (flank), thorax (lateral), and breast (lateral) were chosen as sampling sites due to their high contamination rates. Swabbing selected carcasses involved placing a sterile template (10 × 10 cm) on particular sites of the carcass. A sterile cotton-tipped swab (2 x 3 cm) with a shaft was soaked in approximately 10 ml of buffered peptone water (Oxoid Ltd., Hampshire, England) before

being wiped horizontally and vertically numerous times on the carcasses.

After the rubbing procedure, the shaft was broken by pressing it against the inner wall of the test tube and discarded, leaving the cotton swab in the test tube. A 25-gram sample of raw whole pieces of meat was obtained from each establishment and immersed in buffered peptone water. All samples were brought to the biology lab by ice box for microbiological investigation. Upon arrival, the samples were kept in the refrigerator at 4°C for 24 hours before being processed for isolation.

Sample Collection Procedure for Water Samples

Water sample collection was conducted out in accordance with Iwu et al. (2021). A grab sampling of water samples from two distinct streams that are commonly used for cattle drinking and washing were collected in thoroughly cleansed and sanitized 1 L sample bottles with an air gap at the top to avoid cross contamination. The samples were delivered to the biology laboratory via an ice box for microbiological investigation. All samples were initially screened for *E. coli*, and all positive isolates were then screened for *E. coli* O157: H7.

Sample Collection Procedure for Soil

According to the procedures described by Iwu et al., (20121) soil samples were gathered from several agricultural fields growing potato, cabbage, carrot, red chillies, and tomatoes in sterile plastic bags. Before sampling, it was confirmed that these crops were being planted with animal dung as fertilizer. All obtained soil samples were placed in separate sterile plastic bags, labeled, and delivered to the Microbiology Laboratory/Department of Biology for *E. coli* isolation. All samples were initially screened for *E. coli*, and all positive isolates were then screened for *E. coli* O157: H7.

Preparation of Meat Samples for *E. coli* O157: H7 Isolation

Meat samples were prepared in accordance with Bekele et al. (2021). Each carcass swab was homogenized with a vortex mixer, and 25 g of raw entire slices of meat gathered from each

shop were removed from the universal container, aseptically diced, and homogenized at high speed for 2 minutes using a homogenizer (Stomacher 400, Seward Medical, England). The resultant suspension was utilized to isolate *E. coli* O157:H7.

Isolation Procedure

E. coli was isolated using the method described by Bekele et al. (2021). A 200 µl homogenized beef sample was streaked onto MacConkey agar (IVD, UK) plates and incubated at 37°C for 24 hours. Lactose-positive (pink) colonies were streaked onto Sorbitol-MacConkey Agar plates (IVD, UK) and cultured for 24 hours at 37°C. Sorbitol-negative colorless colonies were subcultured on Rainbow agar.

Rainbow Agar O157 (Hayward, USA) was inoculated by distributing probable *E. coli* colonies on the surface. The plates were then incubated for 24 hours at 37°C and checked for the existence of colored colonies. The unique black or gray appearance of *E. coli* O157: H7 colonies was immediately seen by placing the Petri dish against a white background. The isolated *E. coli* O157: H7 colonies were black or gray when subcultured (BiOLOG User Guide 2008).

Processing of Samples and Enumeration of *E. coli* O157:H7 Isolates

Water samples were serially diluted, as described by Adefisoye et al. (2016). A 100 milliliter aliquot of the dilutions was filtered using 0.45 µm pore size and 37 mm diameter membrane filters (Merck, SA) with a vacuum pump.

After filtering, the filters were aseptically transferred to plates with Sorbitol-MacConkey agar (SMA) (Merck, SA) augmented with cefixime (50 µg/L) and tellurite (25 mg/L) for the enumeration of *E. coli* O157: H7. To enumerate, 100 µL of each dilution was added to pre-prepared SMA (Merck, SA) with cefixime (50 µg/L) and tellurite (25 mg/L) and spread equally with a sterile glass spreader, as reported by Cheesbrough (2006). All plates were then incubated for 24 hours at 37 degrees Celsius. Following incubation, the target isolates were identified using morphology, numbered, and

documented. Colourless colonies were identified as presumptive *E. coli* O157:H7.

Isolation of *E. coli* from Soils

Iwu et al. (2021) described how *E. coli* were isolated from soils. Each gram of soil sample was homogenized in a sterile electrical blender before being suspended in 9 ml of sterile physiological saline (0.85% NaCl). The soil suspension was then serially diluted using the method described by Ogunmwoyi et al. (2008). Serial dilutions up to 10⁻⁷ were prepared, and 1 ml of each dilution was plated on Eosin Methylene Blue (EMB) and Mac Conkey agars.

The plates were incubated at 37 °C for 24 hours. Colonies with a metallic shine on EMB agar and a pink tint on Mac Conkey agar were subcultured to produce pure culture. Pure cultures were biochemically analyzed using API 20 E strips (Bio Merieux, France) to establish their identity as *E. coli*.

Isolation of *E. coli* O157:H7

For enrichment, 10 mL of each water sample and 10 g of soil sample were added to 90 mL of Trypticase soy broth (Merck, SA) and incubated at 37°C for 24 hours. A loop of the broth was then streaked on SMA augmented with cefixime (50 µg/L) and tellurite (25 mg/L) and incubated under the same conditions. After incubation, presumptive colonies were kept in 25% glycerol at -80 °C for further analysis. All presumed isolates were kept in glycerol stocks.

Identification of *E. coli* O157: H7

Pure cultures of all positive *E. coli* isolates from vegetables and water sources were grown on Cefixim Tellurite Sorbitol-MacConkey (CT-SMAC) agar according to the approved protocol and incubated at 37°C for 24 hours. Iwu et al. (2021) used a slide agglutination test with *E. coli* O157: H7 antiserum to confirm suspected *E. coli* O157: H7 colonies.

Confirmatory Test by Latex Agglutination

The test followed the manufacturer's instructions (Oxoid Ltd., Hampshire, England). Before the experiment, the latex kit was tested for performance using the control suspensions included with the kit, and the test was proceeded

once the positive control reacted with the test latex, yielding a positive result. A drop of test latex and 0.085% sterile saline water were added to the reaction card individually. A sterile inoculating needle was gently used to retrieve up to five putative *E. coli* O157: H7 colonies. The selected colonies were fully emulsified with saline on a latex card, followed by the test latex reagent. The production of agglutination within one minute was considered positive.

Antimicrobial Susceptibility Testing

Antimicrobial susceptibility testing was performed according to Nega Desalegn et al. (2021). *E. coli* O157: H7 isolates were tested in vitro for susceptibility to nine routinely used antimicrobial medicines using the disk diffusion method. A test suspension was made from a pure culture of *E. coli* O157: H7 isolates, which was then injected into a test tube containing 5 ml of TSB (Himedia, India) and incubated for 6 hours at 37°C. - The bacterial suspension was adjusted to meet 0.5 McFarland turbidity criteria. Mueller-Hinton agar plates (Bacton Dickinson, USA) were prepared in accordance with the manufacturer's instructions. The diluted bacterial solutions were swabbed uniformly in three directions on the surface of Mueller-Hinton agar plates with sterile cotton swabs.

After the plates had dried, antibiotic-impregnated disks (Oxoid, England) were placed on the inoculation plates using sterile thumb forceps. The plates were then incubated aerobically at 37 degrees Celsius for 24 hours. Finally, the diameter of the inhibition zone generated around each disk was measured on a black surface with a transparent ruler placed over the plates. The findings were categorized as sensitive, moderate, and resistant.

Data Analysis

The data was imported into MS Excel and then analysed with SPSS version 21. The overall prevalence of *E. coli* O157: H7 in different samples was calculated using a standard formula. Descriptive statistics such as proportions were used. The overall and sample-specific prevalence were calculated by dividing the number of positive samples by the total number of samples analyzed, multiplied by 100. The chi-square (χ^2) test was used to compare proportions of groups based on specific determining factors. A p-value of <0.05 indicated a statistically significant difference.

Results & Discussions

Prevalence of *E. coli* O157:H7 in Beef Meat

The incidence of *E. coli* O157: H7 in beef flesh samples was determined using a cross-tabulation analysis of various sample types, including beef mucosal swab, beef carcass inside, beef carcass outside, and beef skin swab (Table 1). Out of the 80 samples evaluated, 25% tested positive for *E. coli* O157: H7, with 0% in beef mucosal swab samples, 1.3% in beef carcass interior samples, and 2.5% in beef carcass outside samples. The highest incidence was found in beef skin swab samples, when 3.8% tested positive for *E. coli* O157: H7. In contrast, 75% of the samples tested negative for the pathogen, with varied levels of negativity across sample types. Specifically, 25% of beef mucosal swab samples, 23.8% of beef carcass interior samples, 25% of beef carcass exterior samples, and 22.5% of beef skin swab samples were negative for *E. coli* O157: H7. These findings shed light on the distribution and prevalence of the virus in various beef meat sample types, emphasizing the significance of focused monitoring and control actions to assure food safety.

Table 1. Cross Tabulation Results of Prevalence of E. coli O157: H7 in Beef Meat

			Sample Type				Total
			Beef Mucosal swab	Beef Carcass inside	Beef Carcass outside	Beef Skin swab	
Number	Positive	Count	0	1	0	2	3
		% of Total	0.0%	1.3%	0.0%	2.5%	
	Negative	Count	20	19	20	18	77
		% of Total	25.0%	23.8%	25.0%	22.5%	96.3%
Total		Count	20	20	20	20	80
		% of Total	25.0%	25.0%	25.0%	25.0%	100.0%

Note: Number * Sample Type Cross tabulation

The statistical analysis yielded a chi-square value of 3.810 and a corresponding p-value of .283, showing that there was no significant relationship between the sample types and the prevalence of E. coli O157:H7. These findings

shed light on the pathogen's distribution in various beef meat sample types, which might inform future research and control methods to assure food safety, as shown in Table 2.

Table 2. Prevalence of E. coli O157: H7 in Beef Meat

S.No.	Sample type	Samples Examined	% Prevalence	χ^2	p-value
1	Skin swab	20	2.50	3.810	.283
2	Mucosal swab	20	0		
3	Carcass outside	20	0		
4	Carcass inside	20	1.25		
	Total	80	3.75		

Prevalence of E. coli O157:H7 in Sheep Meat

The incidence of E. coli O157: H7 in sheep meat samples was determined using a cross-tabulation of several sample types, which included sheep carcass inside, sheep carcass outside, sheep mucosal swab, and sheep skin swab (Table 3). Out of the 80 samples evaluated, 25% tested positive for E. coli O157: H7. In particular, 1.3% of sheep carcass inside samples and 1.3% of sheep carcass exterior samples proved positive for the virus. No prevalence was found in sheep mucosal swabs, however 3.8% of sheep skin swabs tested positive for E. coli O157: H7. In

contrast, 75 samples (93.8%) proved negative for the pathogen, with the percentages changing depending on the sample type.

Notably, 25% of sheep carcass interior samples, 25% of sheep carcass exterior samples, 25% of sheep mucosal swabs, and 21.3% of sheep skin swabs tested negative for E. coli O157:H7. These findings shed light on the distribution and prevalence of the virus in various sheep meat sample types, stressing the significance of monitoring and control measures to assure food safety, as illustrated in Table 3.

Table 3. Prevalence of E. coli O157: H7 in Sheep Meat

			Sample Type				Total
			Sheep Carcass inside	Sheep Carcass outside	Sheep Mucosal swab	Sheep Skin swab	
Number	Positive	Count	1	1	0	3	5
		% of Total	1.3%	1.3%	0.0%	3.8%	

	Negative	Count	19	19	20	17	75
		% of Total	23.8%	23.8%	25.0%	21.3%	93.8%
Total		Count	20	20	20	20	80
		% of Total	25.0%	25.0%	25.0%	25.0%	100.0%

Note: Number * Sample Type Crosstabulation

The statistical analysis produced a chi-square value of 4.053 and a corresponding p-value of .256, showing that there was no significant relationship between the sample types and the prevalence of E. coli O157:H7. These findings

provide useful insights into the pathogen's distribution in various sheep meat sample types, which may be used to improve targeted monitoring and control methods to assure food safety (Table 4).

Table 4. Prevalence of E. coli O157: H7 in Sheep Meat

S.No.	Sample type	Samples Examined	% Prevalence	χ^2	p-value
1	Skin swab	20	3.75	4.053	.256
2	Mucosal swab	20	0		
3	Carcass outside	20	1.25		
4	Carcass inside	20	1.25		
	Total	80	6.25		

Prevalence of E. coli O157:H7 in Goat Meat

The prevalence of E. coli O157: H7 in goat meat samples was evaluated (Table 5) using a cross-tabulation analysis of several sample types, such as goat carcass inside, goat carcass outside, goat mucosal swab, and goat skin swab. Out of the 80 samples tested, 25% were positive for E. coli O157:H7. In particular, 1.3% of goat carcass inside samples and 1.3% of goat carcass exterior samples proved positive for the virus. E. coli O157: H7 was not detected in goat mucosal swab samples, however 2.5% of goat skin swab samples tested positive.

In contrast, 76 samples (95%) proved negative for the pathogen, with variable levels of negativity across sample categories. Specifically, 23.8% of goat carcass interior samples, 23.8% of goat carcass exterior samples, 25% of goat mucosal swab samples, and 22.5% of goat skin swab samples tested negative for E. coli O157: H7. These findings shed light on the distribution and prevalence of the virus in various goat meat sample types, emphasizing the significance of focused monitoring and control strategies to ensure food safety, as shown in Table 5.

Table 5 Cross Tabulation Results of Prevalence of E. coli O157: H7 in Goat Meat

		Sample Type					Total
		Goat Carcass inside	Goat Carcass outside	Goat Mucosal swab	Goat Skin swab		
Number	Positive	Count	1	1	0	2	4
		% of Total	1.3%	1.3%	0.0%	2.5%	5.0%
	Negative	Count	19	19	20	18	76
		% of Total	23.8%	23.8%	25.0%	22.5%	95.0%
Total		Count	20	20	20	20	80
		% of Total	25.0%	25.0%	25.0%	25.0%	100.0%

Note: Number * Sample Type Crosstabulation

The statistical analysis produced a chi-square value of 2.105 and a corresponding p-value of .551, showing that there was no significant relationship between sample types and the prevalence of *E. coli* O157: H7 in goat meat

samples. These findings provide important insights into the pathogen's distribution in various sample types, which can guide future research and control efforts to assure the safety of goat meat products (Table 6).

Table 6. Prevalence of *E. coli* O157: H7 in Goat Meat

S.No.	Sample type	Samples Examined	% Prevalence	χ^2	p-value
1	Skin swab	20	2.5	2.105	.551
2	Mucosal swab	20	0		
3	Carcass outside	20	1.25		
4	Carcass inside	20	1.25		
	Total	80	5.0		

Prevalence of *E. coli* O157:H7 Among Food Business Operators

A cross-tabulation analysis was performed to examine the prevalence of *E. coli* O157: H7 in meat samples from abattoirs and retailers (Table 7). A total of 240 samples were tested, and 12 (5.0%) were positive for *E. coli* O157: H7.

Abattoirs had a higher proportion of positive samples, with 8 (3.3%) compared to 4 (1.7%) in store samples. The chi-square value for the study was 6.316, with a p-value of 0.012, demonstrating a statistically significant relationship between the type of shop (abattoir or retailer) and the prevalence of *E. coli* O157: H7 in the meat samples.

Table 7. Prevalence of *E. coli* O157: H7 Among Food Business Operators

			Type of Shop		Total	χ^2	p-value
			Abattoir	Retailer			
Number	Positive	Count	8	4	12		
		% of Total	3.3%	1.7%	5.0%		
	Negative	Count	72	156	228	6.316	0.012
		% of Total	30.0%	65.0%	95.0%		
Total		Count	80	160	240		
		% of Total	33.3%	66.7%	100.0%		

Further analysis of the data reveals that 30.0% of slaughterhouse samples tested negative for the infection, whereas 65.0% of merchant samples tested negative. The overall distribution of positive and negative samples reveals that 33.3% came from abattoirs and 66.7% from merchants. These findings demonstrate that the prevalence of *E. coli* O157: H7 may fluctuate between meat samples received from abattoirs and merchants, emphasizing the significance of monitoring and control methods at various stages in the meat supply chain to ensure food safety. The overall prevalence of *E. coli* O157: H7 (5.0%) in beef

meat from both the abattoir and retailer shops was higher than findings from 1.3% in Addis Abeba (Abdissa et al., 2017), 2.7% in Haramaya University (Taye et al., 2013), and less than findings from Ambo 23.4% (Nega Desalegn et al., 2021), Tigray 10.4% (Abebe et al., 2014), Debre Zeyit 8% (Hiko et al., 2008), and Mekele 6.7% (Endale et al., 2014). The variations in the prevalence of *E. coli* O157:H7 could be attributed to sample size, sampling methodology, laboratory methodologies, and research location. In terms of meat business operators, higher contamination of *E. coli* O157:

H7 was found at the abattoir (3.3%) than at retailer shops (1.7%), which contradicted the results obtained in Ambo (Nega Desalegn et al., 2021), where the incidence of E. coli O157: H7 was higher in retailer shops (19.1%) than at the

abattoir (7.2%). The greater frequency of E. coli O157: H7 in abattoir shops could be attributed to filthy working conditions and direct contact between workers' contaminated clothing and carcass.

Table 8. Cross Tabulation Results of Prevalence of E. coli O157: H7 in Soil Samples

			Sample Type					Total
			S _{Cabbage}	S _{Carrot}	S _{Potato}	S _{Red chillies}	S _{Tomato}	
Number	Positive	Count	0	2	1	1	0	4
		% of Total	0.0%	2.0%	1.0%	1.0%	0.0%	4.0%
	Negative	Count	20	18	19	19	20	96
		% of Total	20.0%	18.0%	19.0%	19.0%	20.0%	96.0%
Total		Count	20	20	20	20	20	100
		% of Total	20.0%	20.0%	20.0%	20.0%	20.0%	100.0%

Note: Number * Sample Type Crosstabulation

As indicated in Table 8, the prevalence of E. coli O157: H7 in soil samples was determined using a cross-tabulation analysis. A total of 100 soil samples were tested, and 4 (4.0%) tested positive for E. coli O157: H7. The investigation revealed that prevalence rates varied between vegetable-bearing soils. Soil samples containing carrot had the highest prevalence, with 2.0% testing positive for the pathogen, followed by potato and red chili soils, all with a prevalence of 1.0%. E. coli O157: H7 was not detected in cabbage or tomato soil samples.

The overall prevalence of E. coli O157:H7 in agricultural soil samples in the current study (4%) was higher than in the study of Khandaghi

et al., (2010), where only 1.77% of soil samples fertilized with manure in agricultural farms were positive for E. coli O157:H7, but much lower than in the study conducted by Iwu et al. (2021) in South Africa. The statistical analysis yielded a chi-square value of 3.646 and a corresponding p-value of 0.456, showing that there was no significant relationship between the various vegetable bearing soils and the incidence of E. coli O157: H7. These findings provide useful insights into the pathogen's distribution in soil samples from diverse crop varieties, which can drive future research and control methods to reduce the risk of contamination and ensure food safety in the vegetable production process, as shown in Table 9.

Table 9. Prevalence of E. coli O157: H7 in Soil Samples

S.No.	Soil Sample	Samples Examined	% Prevalence	χ^2	p-value
1	S _{Cabbage}	20	0	3.646	.456
2	S _{Carrot}	20	2.0		
3	S _{Potato}	20	1.0		
4	S _{Tomato}	20	0		
5	S _{Red chillies}	20	1.0		
	Total	100	4		

The prevalence of E. coli O157: H7 in Lagabora stream waters was examined, and the results verified the presence of this pathogenic strain (Table 10). A cross-tabulation was used to determine the prevalence of E. coli O157:H7 in

water samples collected from several points in streams, including Sc (Cattle contact point), Sd (Downstream), and Sm (Mid-point). A total of 30 water samples were tested, and two (6.7%) tested positive for E. coli O157: H7. Specifically,

one sample (3.3%) from Sc (Cattle contact point) and one sample (3.3%) from Sm (Mid-point) tested positive for the pathogen, but no positive samples were discovered in Sd (Downstream). The bulk of the water samples tested negative for *E. coli* O157: H7, with various percentages of negatives depending on the sample type. Notably, 30.0% of the samples from Sc (Cattle contact point), 33.3% from Sd (Downstream), and 30.0% from Sm (Mid-point) tested negative

for the virus. The overall distribution of positive and negative samples shows that 6.7% tested positive for *E. coli* O157: H7 and 93.3% were negative. These findings shed light on the prevalence of *E. coli* O157: H7 in water samples from various sites along streams, emphasizing the need of monitoring and control methods to assure water quality and reduce the danger of contamination in the environment.

Table 10. Cross Tabulation Results of Prevalence of *E. coli* O157: H7 in Lagabora Stream

			Sample Type in streams			Total
			Sc (Cattle contact point)	Sd (Downstream)	Sm (Mid-point)	
Number	Positive	Count	1	0	1	2
		% of Total	3.3%	0.0%	3.3%	6.7%
	Negative	Count	9	10	9	28
		% of Total	30.0%	33.3%	30.0%	93.3%
Total		Count	10	10	10	30
		% of Total	33.3%	33.3%	33.3%	100.0%

Note: Number * Sample Type Crosstabulation

The statistical analysis yielded a chi-square value of 1.071 and a p-value of 0.585. These findings show that there was no significant relationship

between the various sites in streams and the incidence of *E. coli* O157: H7 in water samples (Table 11).

Table 11. Prevalence of *E. coli* O157: H7 in Lagabora Stream

S.No.	Sample ID	Samples Examined	% Prevalence	χ^2	p-value
1	Sc (Cattle contact point)	10	3.33	1.071	.585
2	Sm (Mid-point)	10	3.33		
3	Sd (Downstream)	10	0		
	Total	30	6.66		

Waterborne transmission of *E. coli* O157:H7 has been recorded in both recreational and drinking waterways from throughout the world. In the current study, an attempt was made to examine the occurrence of *E. coli* O157: H7 in one stream in Negele town, Lagabora, which is a popular spot for cattle drinking and washing. The water sources studied in this study were surface waters that were susceptible to a variety of pollution sources such as runoff, animal infiltration, and the release of agricultural waste. All water samples from the Lagabora stream, with the exception of those collected from Sd (Downstream), were found to be contaminated

with *E. coli* O157:H7 at a prevalence rate of 6.66%, rendering them unfit for other uses and making these waters potential transmission routes of *E. coli* O157:H7, consistent with previous reports (Myataza et al., 2017). The significant occurrence of *E. coli* O157:H7 in water samples observed in this study was also linked to the vulnerability of most water sources to a variety of anthropogenic activities, including trash dumping, effluent discharge, livestock and human excreta, etc. These are probable sources of *E. coli* O157:H7, which reduces the quality of the water sources.

Antimicrobial Resistance Pattern of *E. coli* O157:H7

The study investigated the antimicrobial susceptibility patterns of bacterial isolates to numerous medicines, each having a varied disc potency (Table 12). Of the 14 isolates tested for Streptomycin (10 µg), 21.42% were susceptible, 35.71% had intermediate resistance, and 42.85% were resistant. For Sulfamethoxazole (100 µg), 28.57% of isolates were susceptible, 14.28% had intermediate resistance, and 57.14% were resistant. Interestingly, none of the isolates were sensitive to Cefoxitin (30 µg), with 57.14% exhibiting intermediate resistance and 42.85% resistant. Tetracycline (30 µg) exhibited 28.57% susceptibility, no intermediate resistance, and 71.42% resistance.

Doxycycline (30 µg) showed 64.28% susceptibility, 35.71% intermediate resistance, and no cases of resistance. Ampicillin (25 µg) demonstrated 28.57% susceptibility, 42.85% intermediate resistance, and 28.57% resistance.

Ciprofloxacin (5 µg) showed 57.14% susceptibility and 42.85% resistance, without intermediate resistance. Trimethoprim (5 µg) had no susceptible isolates, 50% exhibited intermediate resistance, and 50% were resistant. Gentamicin (10 µg) resulted in 42.85% susceptibility, 21.42% intermediate resistance, and 35.71% resistance. These findings provide a thorough understanding of the antimicrobial susceptibility patterns of bacterial isolates to various medications, which will aid in clinical decision-making and antimicrobial stewardship activities.

In the current study, 12 of 14 isolates were sensitive to streptomycin, sulfamethoxazole, tetracycline, doxycycline, ampicillin, ciprofloxacin, and gentamicin, which is comparable with the findings of Bekele et al. (2021) from Ethiopia. The bulk of the isolates are antibiotic susceptible, which is consistent with the findings of Rangel and Marin (2009) and Rahimi and Nayeypour (2012).

Table 12. Antimicrobial Susceptibility Pattern of *E. coli* O157: H7 Isolates

S.No.	Drug	Disc potency (µg)	Number of isolates	Number of isolates (%) showing antimicrobial susceptibility		
				Susceptible N (%)	Intermediate N (%)	Resistant N (%)
1	Streptomycin	10 µg	14	3 (21.42)	5 (35.71)	6 (42.85)
2	Sulfamethoxazole	100 µg	14	4 (28.57)	2 (14.28)	8 (57.14)
3	Cefoxitin	30 µg	14	0 (0.0)	8 (57.14)	6 (42.85)
4	Tetracycline	30 µg	14	4 (28.57)	0 (0.0)	10 (71.42)
5	Doxycycline	30 µg	14	9 (64.28)	5 (35.71)	0 (0.0)
6	Ampicillin	25 µg	14	4 (28.57)	6 (42.85)	4 (28.57)
7	Ciprofloxacin	5 µg	14	8 (57.14)	0 (0.0)	6 (42.85)
8	Trimethoprim	5 µg	14	0 (0.0)	7 (50.0)	7 (50.0)
9	Gentamicin	10 µg	14	6 (42.85)	3 (21.42)	5 (35.71)

Conclusions

The aforementioned research revealed the presence of the *E. coli* O157: H7 strain in all of the sources examined in Negele town. *E. coli* O157: H7 was detected at low levels in feces, intestinal mucosal swabs, and skin swabs taken from both abattoirs and retail stores. The isolation of *E. coli* O157: H7 from feces and intestinal mucosal swabs suggests that the pathogen was carried by the animal. Despite its

low incidence, *E. coli* O157: H7 has a significant public health impact due to its low infective dosage. All water samples from the Lagabora stream, with the exception of those obtained from Sd (Downstream), were found to be polluted with *E. coli* O157:H7 at a prevalence rate of 6.66%, leaving them inappropriate for other uses and making these waters possible *E. coli* O157:H7 transmission routes. There is little information on the prevalence of *E. coli*

O157:H7 in agricultural soils in Ethiopia, and the current study found that the total frequency of *E. coli* O157:H7 in agricultural soil samples was 4%. Agricultural soil is virtually unavoidably contaminated with pathogens like *E. coli* O157:H7 because it is exposed to both direct and indirect sources of microbial pollutants such as animal dung, runoff, polluted irrigation water, and free-range animals. Consumption of vegetables contaminated with *E. coli* O157:H7 has been linked to numerous epidemics around the world. The current investigation found variance in the prevalence of *E. coli* O157:H7 in soils with different crops growing. *E. coli* O157:H7 was detected in soils growing red chillies, potatoes, and carrots, but no positive cases were found in soils growing tomato or cabbage. The discrepancy was ascribed to the use of inadequately decomposed animal dung to enrich the soil. The use of bovine dung as fertilizer, as well as the closeness of vegetable fields or water supplies to cattle farms, have all been linked to vegetable contamination. Employing good agricultural practices such as constant cleaning of farm tools, establishing hedges around the farm to prevent unwanted animal intrusion, effective treatment of organic fertilisers before application to the soil, and the use of clean water for irrigation, as well as good irrigation methods, will help to prevent the occurrence and spread of pathogenic bacteria such as *E. coli* O157:H7 to fresh vegetable products. The majority of the identified strains of *E. coli* O157:H7 have evolved multidrug resistance to two or more drugs. As a result, this pathogen poses a high risk of infection for users. The public health dangers posed by *E. coli* O157:H7 contamination from multiple sources must be addressed at all levels, from public health personnel to municipal administration in the current study region.

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